

SINGAPORE EXPERIENCE IN EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF GOVERNMENT BODIES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6481691>

Akhmedov Azizhon Muxsinjon ogli

PhD student of the National University of Uzbekistan

In increasing the efficiency of public administration The experience of Germany and Britain serves as a model for a number of European countries. However, their implementation in the industry is not carried out directly in any country, that is, it can be seen that each country implements such reforms based on its socio-cultural needs. Of course, in order to increase the efficiency of government, it is impossible to say that today new technologies are developed only in some countries and applied in others. Modern development plans are unique to each country. In particular, in the countries of the East, one can find the best practices that are being presented to the world today. In this regard, Japan and Singapore can be the object of appropriate analysis.

Singapore, like Japan, has a unique experience in improving the efficiency of public administration. It identifies the active introduction of innovative technologies in public administration as a priority of strategic development. In addition to outsourcing, crowdsourcing, benchmarking methods, blockchain technologies, the principle of meritocracy has been widely introduced in improving the efficiency of public administration .

Singapore is a parliamentary republic and the government is accountable to parliament. The government is responsible for planning and monitoring the state budget . It should be noted that despite the authoritarian nature of Singapore's public administration, its social order, principles of justice and economic development have not faltered. The American scholar Francis Fukuyama calls Singapore's system of governance "soft authoritarianism ."

Another area of focus in Singapore's public policy is the wise training of qualified civil servants. According to expert scholars, the high level of professionalism of public services and strict adherence to the rules of ethics play an important role in the effectiveness of public administration in practice . In this regard, German Chancellor Otto von Bismarck said, "No matter how levelless the laws are, it is possible to run a government

effectively with good civil servants. However, even good laws cannot help a government with low-level civil servants,"he said.

In 1951, the Public Service Commission (PSC) was established in Singapore to ensure the effectiveness of public administration. The main functional task of the commission was to systematize the analysis of issues such as the organization of the civil service, the formation of a reserve of candidates, selection, promotion. The most important and noteworthy aspect is that the composition of the commission is composed of personnel who have not previously worked in the civil service . As a result, the commission's independence from the government and an objective approach to various processes were ensured.

Later, the work of this commission was improved, some functions and powers were revised. Particularly radical changes were made in 1994 by President Lee Kuan Yew . In particular, the powers of the commission, such as the formation of human resources, the organization of the civil service, promotion, were transferred to ministries and departments . The commission was only given the function of appointing me to my post in a transparent manner. To date, the work of the commission has been further improved and it deals with the following issues:

- appointment of experienced, mature specialists to senior government positions;
- analysis of the effectiveness of the civil service of ministries and departments;
- resolving problems and conflicts related to appointments to positions;
- effective management of collaborative management programs.

Our analysis shows that Confucian values and paternalistic attitudes play an important role in public administration in Singapore. At the same time, the decentralization of public administration, the outsourcing of many public services or the transfer of all public services to private organizations, leads to the definition and efficiency of ministries and agencies in the field of priorities and tasks.

In this regard, it should be noted that the introduction of market mechanisms in the system of governance of developed capitalist countries is explained by the fact that the control function of the state plays the role of developing market relations. In our opinion, such an approach allows for tactical and strategic planning, as well as the timely completion of important tasks.

When one focuses on the essence of the Singapore public administration model, one can observe that it is socially oriented. This is manifested as follows: first, the consistency of the strategic plan and tactical goals; second, the rapid flexibility of public policy and its implementation mechanisms; third, that market relations are the main direction in the management system; fourth, the accountability of public authorities to citizens and the existence of strong public scrutiny .

In order to increase the efficiency of the public administration system in Singapore, special attention will be paid to the education system as a priority in order to develop human resources. In particular, the network of Civil Service Colleges (CSC-Civil Service Colleges) has played an important role in the formation and development of the civil service. The first Civil Service College was established in 1971 to teach students how to apply the latest innovative approaches to the management system in education. The Civil Service College Act of 2001 also established a legal framework for colleges . A number of initiatives have been put forward by civil service colleges to improve governance. In particular, the institute of mentoring, which is an important tool for improving management efficiency, has been developed and widely implemented . It should be noted that many special programs have been developed in Singapore in this regard.

Our observations show that in order to ensure the effective functioning of public administration, the government has established a systematic relationship with society. All appeals of citizens to public administration bodies are promptly considered by civil servants and answered within a short period of time, if they are not answered within a specified period, the responsible representative of the public body is prosecuted in accordance with the law.

Five important skills are formed in the process of professional training of civil servants in civil service colleges:

- the service process must be organized on the basis of high quality;
- manage any changes in the environment;
- to give positivity to citizens in communication;
- resource and process management according to a plan;
- self-management.

Also, the specific high efficiency of public service is based on the factors of iron discipline, diligence, professionalism, reliability, meritocracy, personal example by leaders, constant striving for excellence, high demand by political leaders, systematic reduction of corruption and achieving clearly defined strategic goals. If we analyze the basis of Singapore's

management philosophy in depth, an important issue in it is to achieve efficiency by simplifying the system of public administration, ensuring that it is understandable to all segments of the population. To this end, Singapore launched the MAGENTA (Methodology for Agency Enterprise Architecture) program in 2006 functional chi qdi. The priority of this program was to ensure the integrity of governance, ie to raise the quality of relations between the authorities to a qualitatively higher level (vertical and horizontal) and to increase their overall responsibility to citizens . There are 3 main pillars of the efficiency of public administration in the country. These are the principles of justice, pragmatism and meritocracy.

It should be noted that as a result of the above-mentioned methods, principles of increasing efficiency, attention to human resources, today Singapore occupies a high position in the global innovation index. In addition, more than 50 percent of the population is middle class and has a monthly income equivalent to \$ 5,000 and lives a prosperous life. If you look at Singapore's national legislation, there is no legislation that regulates exactly outsourcing operations. However, guidelines and regulations specific to public authorities may apply to certain types of outsourcing operations, particularly in the financial sector. At the same time, as a result of the perfect structure of bilateral agreements, there are few cases of force majeure. In particular, certain types of professional services in professional services (such as medical, legal, or accounting services) are regulated by certain laws and regulations. These regulated professional services can only be provided by qualified and licensed individuals.

The outsourcing guidelines issued by the Singapore Monetary Agency (MAS) on July 27, 2016 were last revised on October 5, 2018 and came into force on October 8, 2018. It has made it possible to clearly define regulatory requirements for outsourcing for public authorities. The outsourcing guidelines outline the results of a public authority that has entered into any outsourcing agreement or plans to outsource some of its activities to a service provider, and provides sound guidance on outsourcing contract risk management . The main requirements of the outsourcing guidelines are summarized as follows:

- identify the importance of the role of outsourcing in the overall strategy and goals of public authorities;
- conduct comprehensive inspections on the nature, scope and complexity of the outsourcing agreement to identify and reduce risks;

- assessment of the service outsourcer's ability to meet the regulatory standards of the public administration body in the provision of outsourcing services;

- in the process of outsourcing agreement, the public authority to determine the future overall effectiveness and to achieve the availability of internal expertise and resources to reduce the identified risks, as well as their analysis;

- analysis of the advantages of outsourcing against potential risks, in-depth analysis of processes from the effects of temporary minor crises to major crises;

- maintaining security and confidentiality in outsourcing services, preventing the unexpected termination of the outsourcing contract, including ensuring that the outsourcer takes primary responsibility for strategic and internal control;

- the public administration body must be transparent when planning to enter into an outsourcing agreement with an existing or new service outsourcer, as well as planning periodic re-execution of existing outsourcing agreements, and pay attention to the tactical aspects of risk assessment. In addition, the public administration should study the service outsourcers, including the service outsourcer's experience, financial stability, material and technical base, reputation and culture, non-conflict with partners in expected or actual litigation, security, reporting and monitoring environment and risk management scope and capabilities. should have the correct information .

When concluding a contract between a public administration body and an outsourcing company, the terms of the contract governing the relations, obligations and rights of the parties must be carefully and accurately defined in writing and legally enforced. These include the scope of the agreement, standards, confidentiality and security, continuous management of the agreement over the term of the contract, monitoring and control, audit, dispute resolution , early notification of possible problematic events.

The three main reasons for the active use of outsourcing by the Singaporean government are:

- relative simplification of operations in public administration; focus on priorities; ensuring a high level of service quality to citizens.

Public authorities enter into contracts with outsourcing companies on specific elements of their activities, so that it has a direct external outsourcing relationship with several suppliers. The public administration

body may enter into a management agreement to generalize the management of the service outsourcers so that the public authority has more control over the overall service levels. In Singapore, the main methods of resolving disputes between a public administration body and an outsourcing company are litigation and arbitration.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Paxomova L.F. Process models (Singapore, Malaysia, Thailand, Indonesia). - M.: Institute of Oriental Studies RAN, 2007. - 256 p.
2. Fukuyama F. Konets istorii i posledniy chelovek. Per. s. ang. M.B.Levina. - M.: OOO "Izdatelstvo AST", 2004. -588 p.
3. Khan H. Social Policy in Singapore: Confucian model? - New York: World Bank institute, - 2001.docements / worldbank.org / curated / en / 193101468758956946 / Social-policy-in-Singapore-a-Confucian-model
4. The Public Service Commission formed - <https://eresources.nlb.gov.sg/history/events>
5. "Chapter 5 The public service commission" - [https://doi.org/10.1108/S0732-1317\(2010\)0000019010](https://doi.org/10.1108/S0732-1317(2010)0000019010)
6. Eshtieva D.M. Op yt uspushnogo sotsiolnogo upravleniya na primere Singapore / Istoricheskaya i sotsialno-obrazovatel'naya mysl. www.hist.edu.ru
7. The Civil Service College Act-<https://www.cscollege.gov.sg/About/20Us/pages/our-history.aspx>
8. Group Facilitation- www.cscollege.gov.sg/programmes/pages/display20programme
9. Electronic government Singapore - deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/ua/Documents/public-sector/e-government
10. Outsourcing: Singapore overview - Transferring employees on an outsourcing in Singapore: overview
11. Guidelines on Outsourcing - www.mas.gov.sg/regulation/guidelines/guidelines-on-outsourcing